

AGRO4AGRI

Stakeholder-aligned pathways to impact and exploitation in sustainable agrochemistry

Linking scientific innovation with regulatory, market, and societal value

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AGRO4AGRI: TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

A4A consortium is working on the development and exploitation planning for several innovative technology families:

- Novel RNA-i based precision nematicides
- Slow-release fertilisers
- Biostimulants

The overall purpose of the consortium is to develop solutions that will make agriculture more sustainable.

How can we make sure that the technology delivers impact?

CHALLENGE: TRANSLATING RESEARCH INTO REAL WORLD IMPACT

Exploitation planning does not begin at the end of a project!

It should be designed alongside research activities, using stakeholder priorities to guide both evidence generation and exploitation strategy.

PRIORITY SCANNING EXERCISE

- Different stakeholders evaluate innovation through different value lenses.
- Agricultural innovation stakeholder value framework outline (stakeholder list is not exhaustive!):

Stakeholder	Current problems	Innovation uptake barriers	Considerations (more detailed)
Industry	Regulations, R&D costs, shrinking product pipelines	Can this become a commercially viable product?	Differentiation, cost structure, manufacturing feasibility, supply chain, energy and process efficiency, product stability, IP, market potential (demand signal)
End users	Heavy reliance on agrichem, increase in input costs, pest resistance	Does it work reliably and cost-effectively?	Field performance, reliability (of action and supply), ease of use, cost-effectiveness, operational practicality, risk reduction
Regulators	Balancing agricultural productivity needs with environmental safety	Is it demonstrably safe?	Safety evidence, material characterisation, exposure pathways, risk assessment readiness, precedent alignment, monitoring capability

USING STAKEHOLDER PRIORITY SCAN TO INFORM EVIDENCE GENERATION PLANNING

Stakeholder priorities shape what evidence must be generated (from R&D to commercialisation) to directly inform exploitation strategies.

Stakeholder	Priorities	Evidence generation plan
Industry	Can this become a commercially viable product?	Technical feasibility: scalability, batch reproducibility, formulation stability, performance claims Cost structure: cost of goods estimates, supply chain, energy requirements of production. Intellectual property landscape: patentability and freedom to operate.
End users	Does it work reliably and cost-effectively?	Agronomic effectiveness: field performance in different soils/climates, yield increase and its predictability Operational compatibility: compatibility with existing application equipment and farming practices. Economic outcomes: cost per hectare, input reduction potential, return on investment.
Regulators	Is it demonstrably safe?	Environmental fate: degradation pathways, persistence in soil and water, bioaccumulation potential. Ecotoxicology: effects on non-target organisms. Human health assessment: toxicological studies; exposure scenarios.

TRANSLATING EVIDENCE INTO VALUE PROPOSITION

Scientific metrics describe technical performance, whereas stakeholders respond to practical outcomes (how does the innovation solve the problem that they have?).

Research data becomes valuable when it is **framed in terms of positive stakeholder outcomes compared to the existing solutions.**

Stakeholder	How can our technology solve their problem?
Industry	Demonstrate that the technology can be manufactured reliably at competitive cost, integrated into existing production infrastructure, and positioned as a differentiated product in the market. Measure: predominantly monetary (ROI)
End users	Demonstrate reliable field performance and economic benefits, such as reduced input use, lower application frequency, improved yield stability, or simplified management. Measure: yield metrics (kg/ha increase), also monetary (ROI)
Regulators	Show clear reduction in environmental impact and minimal health risk (relative to conventional agrochemicals), supported by safety data. Measure: carbon, time, mortality

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

Stakeholder value mapping should be an integral part of your project.

Feel free to use our stakeholder value framework tool!

What do you recommend for consideration in this framework?

Stakeholder type	Current problems	Innovation uptake barriers	Our solution	Evidence generation needs	Data to value translation	Engagement strategy
Who are the key actors whose decisions determine whether this innovation succeeds?	What practical challenge or unmet need is this stakeholder currently facing?	What is the appetite for innovative solutions and how are they assessed?	How does the innovation address this problem better than existing approaches?	What data must be generated to demonstrate that the solution works and is credible?	How can the evidence be translated into clear benefits for this stakeholder?	How and when should this stakeholder be involved to support adoption and exploitation?

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Thank you for listening!

Please get in touch to discuss how we can support the exploitation planning of your innovation

Jolanta Beinaroviča, PhD

Senior Strategy Consultant at Optimat (UK)

Jolanta.Beinarovica@optimat.co.uk

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